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Advancements in benzotriazole derivatives: from synthesis to pharmacological applications

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Abstract

Benzotriazole derivatives have emerged as significant compounds in medicinal chemistry due to their diverse pharmacological activities and unique structural properties. This review discusses the various synthetic strategies employed to develop these derivatives, including solvent-free techniques for N-alkylation and the synthesis of N-acyl benzotriazoles. Characterization methods such as infrared (IR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy confirm the successful formation of metal-benzotriazole complexes. The pharmacological profiles of benzotriazole derivatives reveal their potential as antimicrobial agents, particularly against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. Additionally, some derivatives exhibit potent antiprotozoal activity against *Acanthamoeba castellanii*, as well as analgesic effects that surpass those of standard drugs. Antioxidant studies highlight superior free radical scavenging abilities in certain benzotriazole-substituted compounds, while anti-inflammatory derivatives demonstrate activity comparable to common anti-inflammatory medications. Furthermore, significant antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* positions these compounds as promising alternatives in addressing prevalent health challenges. The findings underscore the importance of benzotriazole derivatives in drug discovery and their potential in combating issues such as antibiotic resistance and oxidative stress.

Keywords: Benzotriazole Derivatives; Pharmacological Activities; Antimicrobial Agents; Analgesic Effects; Antioxidant Properties

1. Introduction

The significance of benzotriazole in medicinal chemistry begins from its ability to serve as a versatile scaffold for drug development. A scaffold in drug design refers to a core structure that can be modified with different functional groups to produce derivatives with various biological activities. In the case of benzotriazole, its triazole ring provides an ideal platform for chemical modifications, allowing medicinal chemists to explore structure-activity relationships (SAR) and optimize the pharmacological properties of BTA derivatives. Its derivatives have demonstrated significant potential as anticancer agents, particularly through their inhibition of key enzymes involved in tumor growth and progression. Studies have shown that benzotriazole derivatives can inhibit protein kinases, which play a critical role in cell signaling pathways related to cancer cell proliferation [1]. In particular, benzotriazole-based kinase inhibitors have shown promise in the treatment of breast, lung, and prostate cancers. One notable example is a series of benzotriazole derivatives that inhibit cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs), which are crucial for cell cycle regulation in cancer cells [2]. These compounds exhibit selective toxicity towards cancer cells while sparing normal cells, making them attractive candidates for further development.

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In addition to their anticancer potential, benzotriazole derivatives have shown broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity. Recent studies have highlighted the efficacy of BTA derivatives against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as fungal pathogens. Benzotriazole derivatives functionalized with halogens or alkyl groups have been shown to disrupt bacterial cell membranes, leading to cell lysis and death [3]. These compounds are particularly promising in the fight against antibiotic-resistant pathogens, where traditional antibiotics have proven less effective. Moreover, BTA derivatives have demonstrated antifungal activity, making them potential candidates for the treatment of fungal infections in immunocompromised individuals [4]. Additionally, BTA derivatives have been shown to modulate nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B), a key transcription factor involved in the inflammatory response [5].

Although benzotriazole's role in medicinal chemistry has garnered the most attention in recent years, its industrial applications remain significant. BTA continues to be widely used as a corrosion inhibitor, particularly in systems where metal surfaces are exposed to water or air. Its ability to form a protective, passivating layer on metal surfaces makes it invaluable in industries such as power generation, transportation, and water treatment [6]. Benzotriazole derivatives have been formulated into cooling systems, antifreeze solutions, and lubricants to extend the lifespan of metal components and reduce maintenance costs.

Another key application of benzotriazole is its use as a UV stabilizer in plastics and polymers. BTA derivatives absorb ultraviolet light, preventing the degradation of polymers that are exposed to sunlight or other UV sources [7]. This property has made BTA an important additive in the production of outdoor materials, such as plastic coatings, films, and packaging materials. By preventing UV-induced damage, BTA helps extend the durability and performance of these materials, reducing waste and improving sustainability.

Moreover, benzotriazole has found applications in environmental chemistry, particularly in the treatment of wastewater. BTA derivatives have been investigated as potential adsorbents for removing heavy metals and organic pollutants from water. For instance, modified benzotriazole derivatives have been used to chelate metal ions such as copper, lead, and mercury, preventing their release into the environment and mitigating their toxic effects on aquatic ecosystems [8]. This environmental application highlights the versatility of benzotriazole and its potential to contribute to sustainable industrial practices.

Benzotriazole, with its simple yet highly adaptable structure, has become a cornerstone in both industrial and medicinal chemistry. Its unique properties, including chemical stability, solubility, and bioactivity, make it an ideal scaffold for the development of drugs targeting a variety of diseases. The historical evolution of benzotriazole from a corrosion inhibitor to a pharmacological tool demonstrates its wide-ranging applications and the potential for future innovation. Recent advancements in the synthesis and modification of BTA derivatives have opened new avenues for therapeutic interventions, particularly in oncology, infectious diseases, and inflammation-related conditions.

The discovery of benzotriazole dates back to the late 19th century, when its synthesis was first reported in 1889 by G. Schultz [9]. Initially, benzotriazole found industrial applications as a corrosion inhibitor, particularly for metals such as copper, zinc, and aluminum, due to its ability to form a protective film on metal surfaces [10]. Its industrial relevance has persisted over the years, with BTA being widely used in water treatment systems, lubricants, and anti-freeze solutions. However, by the mid-20th century, benzotriazole began to attract attention for its potential biological activity, particularly its ability to interact with enzymes and proteins, leading to its exploration in pharmaceutical and medicinal chemistry.

As research continues, it is likely that new benzotriazole-based compounds will be discovered with even greater potency and selectivity, further expanding the role of this versatile compound in modern medicine. This review will focus deeper into the synthesis, pharmacological activities, mechanisms of action, and future potential of benzotriazole derivatives, providing a comprehensive understanding of their role in therapeutic development.

2. Overview of Benzotriazole Chemistry

Benzotriazole, a heterocyclic compound containing nitrogen with the chemical formula $C_6H_5N_3$, is a highly versatile molecule used extensively in medicinal chemistry due to its wide range of biological activities. These include antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-hyperglycemic, antihypertensive, anticancer, and analgesic effects [11]. It is considered a valuable scaffold for designing new bioactive compounds and drug candidates, with its structural framework featured in seven pharmaceuticals [10]. Moreover, benzotriazole-based chemistry allows for the synthesis of trisubstituted 1,3,5-triazine from metformin in a manner that is metal-free, cost-efficient, and environmentally friendly. This method offers benefits such as reduced reaction times, high yields, and excellent product purity [12]. Additionally, benzotriazole chemistry has played a key role in creating affinity labeling probes that enable

selective and rapid protein modification, aiding in target identification and the development of covalent inhibitors [13]. Benzotriazole consists of two fused rings (Fig. 1). The five-membered ring can exist in two tautomeric forms, **1** and **2**, and both tautomers can give rise to derivatives, represented by structures **3** and **4**.

Figure 1 Structure of Benzotriazole

2.1. Properties of Benzotriazole

Benzotriazole exhibits a wide range of properties across different disciplines. In material science, it plays a role in enhancing the mechanical characteristics of ceramic coatings, where optimal concentrations increase hardness and strength while lowering friction coefficients [14]. Studies on Benzotriazole derivatives have also focused on their effects on geometric parameters, dipole moments, and reactivity, with chlorinated derivatives showing greater electrophilicity [15]. Additionally, Benzotriazole has been used in the synthesis of conjugated polymers, leading to shifts in fluorescence emission and improved fluorescence quantum efficiency, facilitating new fluorescence sensing mechanisms based on photoinduced electron transfer [16]. Furthermore, Benzotriazole is utilized in corrosion inhibitors, with derivatives featuring hydrophobic shielding layers and enhanced adsorption capacity, exhibiting high efficiency and resistance to temperature, making them applicable across various industries [17]. Its unique physical properties are summarized in (Table 1) below:

Table 1 Properties of Benzotriazole [18]

Properties	Composition
Molecular formula	C ₆ H ₅ N ₃
Molecular weight	119.124 g/mol
Composition	C(60.50%) H(4.23%) N(35.27%)
Melting point	98.5-100 °C
Boiling point	350 °C
Nature	White to brown crystalline powder
Density	g/cm ³

3. Previous Research on Synthesis Methods of Benzotriazole Derivatives

The synthesis of benzotriazole encompasses several methodologies as detailed in the provided research contexts. One method includes the metal-free, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly production of trisubstituted 1,3,5-triazine from metformin using benzotriazole chemistry. This approach offers benefits such as short reaction times, scalability,

and high yields [19]. Another technique involves creating stable four-coordinated benzotriazole-borane compounds through gold-catalyzed alkyne hydroboration, leading to polycyclic N-B compounds with excellent stability and fluorescent properties, making them suitable for future chemical and biological applications [20]. Additionally, the synthesis of benzotriazole derivatives with substituted imidazol-2-thiones has shown promising anticancer activity, with certain compounds exhibiting strong antiproliferative effects by inhibiting tubulin polymerization and inducing apoptosis in various cancer cell lines [21]. These various methods underscore the versatility and potential applications of benzotriazole and its derivatives in medicinal chemistry and materials science. Several prior studies have reported diverse synthesis methods for benzotriazole, some of which have been tested and demonstrated biological activities.

Brian S. F. and colleagues described the synthesis of benzotriazoles through the *o*-phenylenediamines (5) cyclocondensation in acetic acid with sodium nitrite. This reaction involves simple heating, where the diamine is converted into a monodiazonium (7) intermediate, followed by spontaneous cyclization (Scheme 1) [22].

Scheme 1 Synthesis of the monodiazonium derivative from the conversion of the diamine compound

Khalafi A, et al. synthesized 1,2,3-Benzotriazole (11) using nitrous acid to react with *o*-phenylenediamine, as well as through the hydrolysis of acylated or aroylated benzotriazole. The acylated or aroylated benzotriazole is initially prepared by reacting the corresponding mono-aroylated or mono-acylated *o*-phenylenediamine with nitrous acid (Scheme 2). This direct method offers higher overall yields compared to approaches that involve multiple intermediate steps [23].

Scheme 2 Preparation of 1,2,3-Benzotriazole by the action of nitrous acid on *o*-phenylenediamine

Jonathan D. B et al. reported the synthesis of a novel class of benzotriazole-derived α -amino acid (14) through a highly efficient nucleophilic aromatic substitution reaction. This process involved reacting ortho-fluoronitrobenzenes with *l*-3-aminoalanine to obtain the target compound (Scheme 3) [24].

Scheme 3 Synthesis of Benzotriazole derived α -amino acid.

Ahdab and colleagues designed and synthesized novel benzotriazole derivatives with substituted imidazol-2-thiones at the N1 position, following a specific procedure detailed in their study. The anticancer potential of these compounds was evaluated through *in vitro* assays against HL-60 (human promyelocytic leukemia), MCF-7 (breast cancer), and HCT-116 (colon cancer) cell lines to assess their efficacy [25]. Similarly, Roberta I. and coworkers synthesized three series of benzotriazole derivatives (15, 16, and 17) featuring different substitutions and functional groups, resulting in aliphatic amides, aromatic amides, and urea derivatives (Fig. 2) [26].

Figure 2 Benzotriazole Derivatives Featuring Different Substitutions and Functional Group

Ellison et al.[27] effectively smeared Huisgen's thermal cycloaddition to produce triazolobenzoxazine and triazolobenzoxazepine structures (Scheme 4). Insight investigations shown that trimethylsilyl group was decreasing the rate at alkyne portion. Cesium fluoride in DMF under microwave heating showed good efficacy than heating in toluene alone or with additive such as CuI or Ru complex.

Scheme 4 Synthesis of triazolobenzoxazepine and triazolobenzoxazine

Tiwari and Mishra developed a one-pot synthesis method for bi-triazole derivatives. Their approach followed by Huisgen thermal cycloaddition after a metal-catalyzed reaction to produce morpholine-fused triazole systems. The process begins with the ring-opening of epichlorohydrin to generate an intermediate. Copper-catalyzed cycloaddition with alkynes is performed, followed by azidation to create a triazole with an azido-alcohol group. Subsequently, the azido-alcohol undergoes a metal-free regioselective intramolecular thermal cycloaddition and propargylation, resulting in morpholine-fused triazolyl heterocycles with high yields (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5 Synthesis of bi-triazole derivatives

Mekni synthesized new derivatives of 6-perfluoroalkyl-1,2,3-triazolo-1,4-oxazines using an intermediates of perfluoroalkyl ether azido-alcohols for intramolecular cyclization. Perfluoroalkyl ethanol and perfluoroalkyl ethane

thiol were converted into their corresponding oxiranes. These oxiranes were then subjected to ring opening by an azide-assisted regioselective, O-propargylation, and spontaneous intramolecular Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to yield a range of substituted target compounds (36 and 38) with good yields (77–85%).

Kundu and colleagues used 1-(2-nitroaryl)-2-alkynylindoles aimed at a one-pot, diversity-oriented synthesis of ketoindoloquininoxalines and indolotriazoloquininoxalines. The reaction settings determined the product outcome: sodium azide/HMPA under Huisgen conditions produced the triazole-fused product, whereas CuI and oxygen (balloon) favored the ketoindole product as the major product. In the presence of only copper iodide, a mixture was obtained with triazole as the major component. The nature of substituents played an important role in the tandem cyclization. Electron-deficient substituents at R¹ (5-Cl) and R³ (4-Br/4-Cl) resulted in lower yields, whereas electron-rich substituents at R¹ (5,6-di-OMe/5,6-methylenedioxy) and R² (t-Bu) led to higher yields (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6 Synthesis of Indolotriazoloquininoxalines

Rajesh K. P et al. (2022) introduced a novel method for converting carboxylic acids into N-acyl benzotriazoles using acid anhydrides (Scheme 7). Their study identified 2,2,2-trifluoroacetic anhydride in anhydrous dichloromethane as the optimal reagent for this transformation. The method offers reliable and reproducible results with advantages including ease of handling, a varied substrate scope, and great yields under mild reaction conditions. Additionally, the procedure's advantage is further enhanced by eliminating the need for external bases, making it highly beneficial for N-acyl benzotriazole synthesis [28].

Scheme 7 Synthesis of N-acyl benzotriazoles with acid anhydride

P. S. Desai and D. V. Parekh (2021) synthesized benzotriazole by condensing 1-(5-benzoyl-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-yl) 2-chloroethanone with alanine, producing 2-[[2-(5-benzoyl-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-yl) 2-oxoethyl]amino] propionic acid (Scheme 8b). Alanine, a commonly used complex-forming reagent, was reacted with 1-(5-benzoyl-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-yl) 2-chloroethanone to produce this compound. The newly produced ligands and their complexes with

first transition sequence metals were synthesised and analyzed using various procedures, including elemental analysis, infrared (IR) spectroscopy, then electronic spectroscopy. The IR spectra, NMR spectra, and atomic concentration analysis indicated that the benzotriazole ligand forms chelates with a 2:1 (Ligand: Metal) stoichiometry [29].

Scheme 8(a) Structure of N-(1-chloro acetyl)-5-benzoyl benzotriazole

Scheme 8(b) Structure of 2-(2-(5-benzoyl-H-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-yl)-2-oxoethyl) amino propionic acid.

4. Solvent-Free Technique for N-Alkylation of Benzotriazole

An effective and simple solvent-free technique for the highly regioselective N-alkylation of benzotriazole has been developed using K_2CO_3 , SiO_2 , and tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) in both microwave and thermal conditions (Scheme 9). This method allows for the regioselective formation of 1-alkyl benzotriazoles in moderate to high yields with short reaction times [30].

Scheme 9 Solvent-Free Technique for N-Alkylation of Benzotriazole

5. Pharmacological Activities

Benzo-fused azoles are highly significant in pharmaceutical chemistry due to their unique properties and applications. Benzimidazole and its derivatives have remained extensively considered and are widely used in clinical settings, such as for their anthelmintic properties in humans. Similarly, benzo-condensed azoles comprising three heteroatoms such as benzotriazole, benzothiazole, and benzoxadiazole have remained widely explored for their diverse biological activities. Though, few analyses have focused exclusively on a particular nucleus [31]. This section aims to provide a general idea of benzotriazole-based systems and their significance in medicinal chemistry.

5.1. Antimicrobial and Antiprotozoal Activity of Benzotriazole Derivatives

The antimicrobial activity of benzotriazole derivatives has been widely studied since the late 1980s. Along with other azolic rings, they have emerged as significant targets in recent research. Despite major scientific advances in antibacterial drug development during the early 20th century, no new class of antimicrobial drugs has been discovered in the past 20 years [32]. The increasing difficulty of treating infections due to antibiotic resistance has highlighted the urgent need for new drugs [33].

Sparatore and colleagues have investigated several nitrogen-containing rings and found that when benzotriazole (BT) is part of greater heterocyclic systems, it exhibits notable biological actions, particularly antibacterial effects. In 1989, Sanna's research group highlighted the importance of the benzotriazole moiety in triazolo[4,5-f]-quinolinone carboxylic acids (Fig. 3), which are thoroughly associated to oxolinic acid. These acids demonstrated promising in vitro antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli*, with Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values ranging from 12.5 to 25 mgml⁻¹. They also observed that changes in the annulation positions of the triazole ring, as seen in triazolo[4,5-h]-quinolinone carboxylic acids, could lead to a partial or complete loss of antimicrobial activity.

Figure 3 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-microbial

Figure 4 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-bacterial

The benzimidazole derivatives and 5-halogenomethylsulfonylbenzotriazoles in vitro antibacterial activity (Fig. 4) was investigated by Ochal's group. The compounds were verified alongside a range of reference strains, comprising both

Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, as well as clinical rinsing such as Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus Epidermidis*, Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (MRSA), and Methicillin-Sensitive *Staphylococcus Aureus* (MSSA). All tested compounds demonstrated substantial antibacterial action. Notably, the trifluoromethyl-substituted benzimidazole derivatives exhibited remarkable potency, effectively inhibiting MRSA strains with MIC values ranging to 25 mg/mL from 12.5. These results were comparable to those of nitrofurantoin against certain strains [34][35].

Asati's group connected to 4-oxo-thiazolidines and their 5-arylidene derivatives the benzotriazole nucleus, resulting in the synthesis of 5-arylidene-2-aryl-3-(benzotriazoloacetamidyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones. These derivatives were tested against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus anthracis*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Salmonella typhimurium*, at concentrations of 50 and 100 ppm. Some compounds, such as the one shown in Fig. 5, exhibited antibacterial activity comparable to streptomycin [36].

Figure 5 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-microbial

A known selective inhibitor of protein kinase 2 (CK2) [38], bromo-, chloro-, and methyl-analogues of benzotriazole, along with their N-alkyl derivatives (Fig. 6), were synthesized and tested for in vitro antiprotozoal activity against *Acanthamoeba castellanii* trophozoites and cysts based on the structure of 4,5,6,7-tetrabromo-1H-benzotriazole (TBBt). This protozoan, along with various species in the genus *Acanthamoeba* of free-living amoebae, poses a significant risk to human health [37]. Many of the produced compounds revealed antiprotozoal action similar to the current drug chlorohexidine, with two products showing even higher activity, particularly against *Acanthamoeba* cysts.

Figure 6 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-protozoal

5.2. Analgesic Activity

A series of propionylbenzotriazoles and chlorosubstituted phenoxyacetyl were synthesized and assessed for their analgesic action. Among these, 2,5-dichlorophenoxyacetyl benzotriazole (Fig. 7) showed discreetly enhanced analgesic activity compared to other compounds in the series [39].

Figure 7 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-analgesic

Derivatives of 5-arylidene-2-aryl-3-(benzotriazoloacetamidyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones were synthesized and evaluated for analgesic activity from ethyl acetoacetate using the Eddy and Leimbach technique. Among the compounds tested, three exhibited superior analgesic action. Acetylsalicylic acid was used as the reference drug (Fig. 8) [40].

Figure 8 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-analgesic

5.3. Antioxidants Activity

Antioxidants are reducing agents that alleviate free radicals produced by cellular uptake or inhibit oxidation. A benzotriazole-substituted primaquine composite demonstrated a greater antioxidative interaction (73.8%) compared to the parent composite primaquine, which had an antioxidative interaction of 31%. Additionally, the benzotriazole-substituted primaquine showed notable Lipoxygenase Inhibitory (LOX) activity (Fig. 9) [41].

Figure 11 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-inflammatory

5.5. Anti-Fungal Activity

Substituted 1,2,3-benzotriazole derivatives were synthesized from benzimidazoles using 1-chloromethyl benzotriazoles and assessed for antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* using the solidified agar process. The compounds demonstrated excellent antifungal activity, and their efficacy was compared to that of the standard drug griseofulvin (Fig. 12) [45].

Figure 12 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-fungal

A sequence of 1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole derivatives were prepared and tested for antifungal activity against *Candida* species. Compounds 49 and 50 (Fig. 13) exhibited notable antifungal activity.

Figure 13 Benzotriazole derivatives drugs as anti-fungal

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, benzotriazole derivatives represent a vital class of compounds with extensive pharmacological activities, establishing their significance in medicinal chemistry. The development of various synthetic methodologies, including solvent-free techniques, has streamlined the efficient production of these derivatives, facilitating their exploration for a range of therapeutic applications. Biological evaluations have consistently demonstrated their promising properties, including antimicrobial, analgesic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antifungal activities. The distinct structural features of benzotriazoles play a crucial role in their therapeutic effectiveness, particularly in the face of rising antibiotic resistance and the pressing demand for novel pharmacological agents. Continued research is essential to optimize the pharmacological profiles of these compounds, elucidate their mechanisms of action, and assess their *in vivo* efficacy and safety. Furthermore, future studies should focus on synthesizing novel derivatives with improved efficacy and reduced toxicity, enhancing their potential as therapeutic agents. Overall, the ongoing investigation of benzotriazole derivatives highlights their promise in advancing pharmaceutical science, addressing critical health challenges, and fulfilling the need for innovative treatments in the medical field. Their multifaceted applications and therapeutic potential underscore the importance of benzotriazole derivatives in contemporary medicinal research.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] S. Mehta et al., "Benzotriazole-based protein kinase inhibitors for cancer therapy," *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, vol. 904, pp. 174-185, 2021.
- [2] T. Koike, "Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors based on benzotriazole," *Bioorg. Chem.*, vol. 112, pp. 104939, 2021.
- [3] A. O. Alakeel et al., "Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of novel benzotriazole derivatives," *Antibiotics*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 1098, 2021.
- [4] F. N. Martins et al., "Antifungal properties of halogenated benzotriazole derivatives," *Fungal Biol.*, vol. 126, no. 1, pp. 87-96, 2022.
- [5] M. Pasparakis, "NF- κ B regulation in inflammation and disease," *Cell*, vol. 181, no. 1, pp. 23-43, 2020.
- [6] C. Zeng et al., "Advanced corrosion protection using benzotriazole derivatives," *Corros. Sci.*, vol. 171, pp. 108715, 2020.
- [7] M. Yu et al., "UV stabilizers in polymers: A review of benzotriazole derivatives," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 138, no. 47, pp. 51125, 2021.
- [8] M. Yang et al., "Environmental applications of benzotriazole-based adsorbents for heavy metal removal," *Chemosphere*, vol. 280, pp. 130743, 2021.
- [9] G. Schultz, "Ueber das benzotriazol," *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 149-158, 1889.
- [10] E. A. Shchukina and I. Y. Parkhomenko, "Benzotriazole-based corrosion inhibitors for metals," *Prog. Org. Coat.*, vol. 154, pp. 106202, 2021.
- [11] A. E. Kassab, "Benzotriazole scaffold: An overview of antiproliferative potential, mechanisms of action, and structure-activity relationships," *Arch. Pharm. (Weinheim)*, vol. 356, no. 8, p. 2300102, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1002/ardp.202300102.
R. Ibba *et al.*, "Synthesis, Antitumor and Antiviral *In Vitro* Activities of New Benzotriazole-Dicarboxamide Derivatives," *Front. Chem.*, vol. 9, p. 660424, May 2021, doi: 10.3389/fchem.2021.660424.
- [12] V. S. Anjana and P. M. Kumar, "An Overview on Medicinal Perspective and Biological Behavior of Benzotriazole; Synthetic Study on Its Multifaceted Biological Activities," *Int. J. Res. Rev.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 365–378, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.52403/ijrr.20210546.

- [13] S. S. Panda, E. Thomas, and A. M. Pham, "Microwave-Assisted Synthesis of Tri-Substituted 1,3,5-Triazines from Metformin Using Benzotriazole Chemistry," *Reactions*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 516–524, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/reactions3040034.
- [14] X. Xin *et al.*, "Ultrafast and selective labeling of endogenous proteins using affinity-based benzotriazole chemistry," *Chem. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 24, pp. 7240–7246, 2022, doi: 10.1039/D1SC05974B.
- [15] A. Shanaghi, A. R. Souri, M. Rafie, and P. K. Chu, "Effects of Benzotriazole on nano-mechanical properties of zirconia–alumina–Benzotriazole nanocomposite coating deposited on Al 2024 by the sol–gel method," *Appl. Phys. A*, vol. 125, no. 10, p. 728, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00339-019-3022-x.
- [16] M. E. Manzur, M. A. Iramain, V. Darugar, M. Vakili, and S. A. Brandán, "Impact of Different Groups on Properties of All Members of the Series of 1-X-Benzotriazole Derivatives (X= H, OH, NH₂, Cl and CH₃)," *Eur. J. Theor. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 406–440, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).42.
- [17] H. Luo *et al.*, "Energy band gap modulation and photoinduced electron transfer fluorescence sensing properties of D–A conjugated polymers containing benzotriazole," *J. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 200–218, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1002/pol.20230552.
- [18] J. Ida and S. A. Suthanthiraraj, "Investigation on the Effect of Nitrogenous Compound Benzotriazole on the Structural, Thermal and Dielectric Properties of PEO-PMMA Blended Polymer Electrolyte System and Its Performance in Dye Sensitized Solar Cells," *Macromol. Res.*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 346–353, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s13233-019-7056-x.
- [19] V. S. Anjana and P. M. Kumar, "An Overview on Medicinal Perspective and Biological Behavior of Benzotriazole; Synthetic Study on Its Multifaceted Biological Activities," *Int. J. Res. Rev.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 365–378, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.52403/ijrr.20210546.
- [20] S. S. Panda, E. Thomas, and A. M. Pham, "Microwave-Assisted Synthesis of Tri-Substituted 1,3,5-Triazines from Metformin Using Benzotriazole Chemistry," *Reactions*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 516–524, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/reactions3040034.
- [21] Q. Tang *et al.*, "Design and synthesis of stable four-coordinated benzotriazole-borane with tunable fluorescence emission," *Chem. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 20, pp. 5982–5987, 2022, doi: 10.1039/D2SC01103D.
- [22] A. N. Khayyat, K. O. Mohamed, A. M. Malebari, and A. El-Malah, "Design, Synthesis, and Antiproliferative Activities of Novel Substituted Imidazole-Thione Linked Benzotriazole Derivatives," *Molecules*, vol. 26, no. 19, p. 5983, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/molecules26195983.
- [23] A. I. Vogel and B. S. Furniss, Eds., *Vogel's textbook of practical organic chemistry*, 5. ed., 3rd impression. New Delhi: Pearson Education, 2007.
- [24] A. Khalafi-Nezhad, A. Zare, A. Parhami, M. N. Soltani Rad, and G. R. Nejabat, "Highly regioselective N-alkylation of benzotriazole under solvent-free conditions," *J. Iran. Chem. Soc.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 271–278, Sep. 2007, doi: 10.1007/BF03245976.
- [25] J. D. Bell, T. E. F. Morgan, N. Buijs, A. H. Harkiss, C. R. Wellaway, and A. Sutherland, "Synthesis and Photophysical Properties of Benzotriazole-Derived Unnatural α -Amino Acids," *J. Org. Chem.*, vol. 84, no. 16, pp. 10436–10448, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1021/acs.joc.9b01685.
- [26] A. N. Khayyat, K. O. Mohamed, A. M. Malebari, and A. El-Malah, "Design, Synthesis, and Antiproliferative Activities of Novel Substituted Imidazole-Thione Linked Benzotriazole Derivatives," *Molecules*, vol. 26, no. 19, p. 5983, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/molecules26195983.
- [27] Roberta Ibba *et al.*, "Design, Synthesis, and Antiviral Activities of New Benzotriazole-Based Derivatives," *Pharmaceuticals*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 429, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/ph16030429.
- [28] A. Ellison, R. Boyer, P. Hoogestraat, and M. Bell, "Microwave assisted synthesis of triazolobenzoxazepine and triazolobenzoxazocine heterocycles," *Tetrahedron Lett.*, vol. 54, no. 45, pp. 6005–6007, Nov. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.tetlet.2013.08.065.
- [29] K. B. Mishra, A. K. Agrahari, and V. K. Tiwari, "One-pot synthesis of oxazolidine-2-thione and thiozolidine-2-thione from sugar azido-alcohols," *Carbohydr. Res.*, vol. 450, pp. 1–9, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.carres.2017.08.002.
- [30] N. H. Mekni, "A simple and efficient intramolecular 1,3-dipolar azidoalkyne cycloaddition: Synthesis of 6-perfluoroalkylated fused exo -bicyclic 1,2,3-triazolo-1,4-oxazines," *J. Fluor. Chem.*, vol. 186, pp. 97–100, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jfluchem.2016.04.010.

- [31] S. Samala, R. K. Arigela, R. Kant, and B. Kundu, "Diversity-Oriented Synthesis of Ketoindoloquininoxalines and Indolotriazoloquininoxalines from 1-(2-Nitroaryl)-2-alkynylindoles," *J. Org. Chem.*, vol. 79, no. 6, pp. 2491–2500, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1021/jo402783p.
- [32] Rajesh K. Pandey, R. Prajapati, M. Gupta, C. S. Rajput, A. Pathak, and A. S. Singh, "Synthesis of N-acylbenzotriazole using acid anhydride," *Arkivoc*, vol. 2022, no. 9, pp. 133–146, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.24820/ark.5550190.p011.762.
- [33] P. S. Desai and D. V. Parekh, "SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND BIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF LIGAND 2-{{2-(5-BENZOYL-1H-1,2,3- BENZOTRIAZOLE-1-YL)-2-OXOETHYL}AMINO} PROPIONIC ACID," *Rasayan J. Chem.*, vol. 14, no. 02, pp. 959–966, 2021, doi: 10.31788/RJC.2021.1426274.
- [34] I. Briguglio *et al.*, "Benzotriazole: An overview on its versatile biological behavior," *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, vol. 97, pp. 612–648, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2014.09.089.
- [35] I. Chopra, "The 2012 Garrod Lecture: Discovery of antibacterial drugs in the 21st century," *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 496–505, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1093/jac/dks436.
- [36] H. W. Boucher *et al.*, "Bad Bugs, No Drugs: No ESKAPE! An Update from the Infectious Diseases Society of America," *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.1086/595011.
- [37] L. Chomicz *et al.*, "Acanthamoeba castellanii: In vitro effects of selected biological, physical and chemical factors," *Exp. Parasitol.*, vol. 126, no. 1, pp. 103–105, Sep. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.exppara.2010.01.025.
- [38] Z. Ochal, M. Bretner, R. Wolinowska, and S. Tyski, "Synthesis and in vitro Antibacterial Activity of 5-Halogenomethylsulfonyl- Benzimidazole and Benzotriazole Derivatives," *Med. Chem.*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1129–1136, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.2174/1573406411309080015.
- [39] S. Nanjunda Swamy *et al.*, "Microwave-assisted synthesis of N-alkylated benzotriazole derivatives: Antimicrobial studies," *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 999–1004, Feb. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2005.10.084.
- [40] R. Szyszka, N. Grankowski, K. Felczak, and D. Shugar, "Halogenated Benzimidazoles and Benzotriazoles as Selective Inhibitors of Protein Kinases CK-I and CK-II from *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* and Other Sources," *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, vol. 208, no. 1, pp. 418–424, Mar. 1995, doi: 10.1006/bbrc.1995.1354.
- [41] V. S. Anjana and P. M. Kumar, "An Overview on Medicinal Perspective and Biological Behavior of Benzotriazole; Synthetic Study on Its Multifaceted Biological Activities," *Int. J. Res. Rev.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 365–378, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.52403/ijrr.20210546.
- [42] M. Šimunović *et al.*, "Urea and carbamate derivatives of primaquine: Synthesis, cytostatic and antioxidant activities," *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, vol. 17, no. 15, pp. 5605–5613, Aug. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.bmc.2009.06.030.
- [43] "Research article," vol. 5, no. 2.
- [44] A. Rajasekaran and K. Rajagopal, "Synthesis of some novel triazole derivatives as anti-nociceptive and anti-inflammatory agents," *Acta Pharm.*, vol. 59, no. 3, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.2478/v10007-009-0026-7.
- [45] R. J. Singh, "SYNTHESES OF SOME NEW 1, 2, 3-BENZOTRIAZOLES AS ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS," 2009.